

X-ray Diffraction Studies of Humic Acid and its Salt and Sol Complexes

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X-ray diffraction analysis of humic acid (HA) and its different complexes with metal salts and sols are reported. From comparison of known compounds of copper and iron salicylates the nature of binding of the HA with the metal ions is predicted.

X-RAY diffraction analysis has been utilised for characterising the nature of soil humic components and their interaction products with metals¹. Naturally occurring soil humic compounds are generally non-crystalline amorphous and irregular hetero-polycondensates of hexagonal benzene rings with appreciable number of disordered aliphatic or alicyclic side chains and functional groups. In X-ray diffraction patterns, these give weak and diffuse lines²⁻⁴.

A diffraction patterns of HA usually shows broad diffuse bands near 3.5 Å (diagnostic criteria)⁵. The intensity and extent of these bands and halos will depend on the constitution of soil humic components⁶, namely degree of aromaticity, nature of aliphatic components such as -COOH, -OH. Some complexities, however, arise in interpretation of X-ray data of various combination products of soil humic compounds with inorganic constituents as the latter consist of metal salts, hydroxides and hydroxide gels. As a result, the diffraction patterns are sometimes cumbersome. An increase in 3.5 Å bands will indicate a decrease in the number of condensed rings and imperfection in structure⁶. X-ray diffraction data, however, indicate the arrangement of carbon atoms in closed or open structures.

The present work deals with the comparative studies of HA complexes with Cu²⁺, Al³⁺ and Fe³⁺ salts and sols.

Experimental

Humic acid used in the investigation was extracted and fractionated from Bigra pond sediment (Burdwan), West Bengal by the standard method⁷. For X-ray analysis, HA and its complexes were vacuum dried at room temperature and the dried materials were powdered in agate mortar very slowly and were subjected to X-ray diffraction analysis (Philips 1010 diffraction unit with Philips 11.54 cm powder camera) for 25 hr.

Results and Discussion

The average molecular weight of HA as measured by electrometric method⁸ has been found to be 2000. The characteristics X-ray diffraction spacings are given in Table 1. X-ray diffraction tracings as obtained from humic acid show three bands which are similar to those obtained for carbon black and are ascribed by Pollack *et al*⁹ to aromatic structure and graphite like layers. However, the present study does not show any 7.5 Å band which was described by them as an indication of the presence of some non-aromatic structure.

It appears from Table 1 that there are some shifts in basal spacings on interaction of humic acid with metal salts and sols. This shift is not complete, original bonds of humic acid are present, besides which new band appears. The new bands may be due to formation of interaction products with metal ions, and the groups responsible for interaction are not fully utilised.

TABLE 1—REPRESENTS DISPLACEMENT OF BAND IN DIFFERENT METAL SALTS AND METALLIC HYDROXIDE SOL COMPLEXES

HA		HA-Cu ²⁺		HA-Cu ²⁺ Sol		HA-Al ³⁺		HA-Al ³⁺ Sol		HA-Fe ³⁺		HA-Fe ³⁺ Sol		Cu(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂) ₂ ·4H ₂ O		Fe(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂) ₂	
d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I
—	—	3.45	mb	3.59	w	3.60	m	3.50	w	3.43	s	3.45	w	3.51	mw	3.51	mw
3.25	s	3.31	m	3.34	m	3.36	mb	3.35	mb	3.35	mw	3.33	m	3.25	m	3.40	m
—	—	2.13	mb	2.15	w	2.14	w	—	—	2.13	w	2.13	vw	3.12	mw	3.19	mw
2.00	s	2.05	mb	2.10	w	2.08	vw	2.10	w	2.12	w	2.12	w	2.70	vw	2.66	vw
1.82	mw	2.00	w	2.01	w	2.06	vw	1.99	s	—	—	1.99	w	—	—	—	—

mw = medium weak, sb = strong broad, s = strong, w = weak, m = medium, mb = medium broad, vw = very weak.

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The d_{100} values of known compounds like $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3)_3$ ¹⁰ are 3.51 Å which show close resemblance to those new bonds obtained for copper and iron complexes of HA. It appears therefore that metal ions like Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} may have combined through -OH or -COOH groups of the corresponding humus acid and are forming salicylic acid type chelates.

A single crystal X-ray analysis of HA and its complexes with salts/sols gave no characteristic spot. The presence of diffused band in the powder X-ray diffraction supports the earlier views^{3,4} that HA or its complexes are mostly amorphous in character.

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